

A WORD ABOUT THE MEANING OF THE WORD

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ANNOTATION

Since the word is a multifaceted and complex linguistic (speech) unit, its place in our life is unique, and in the conditions of modern globalization, the development of science determines the meaning of the word, the meaning of its nominative function, and the scientific role. The purpose of this article is to analyze the classification of riffs and interpretations from a specific linguistic point of view. The article emphasizes that an in-depth study of the word and its logical possibilities is a key factor in the development of New Uzbekistan, the conditions for national growth and the effectiveness of scientific research in our language. In linguistic terms, when studying this unit of speech, the semantic properties of the word, the scope of the semantic field, the onomastic state, denotative and connotative functions in the expression of meaning or concept, the meaningful and structural forms of these functions are analyzed.

Key words: word, speech, unity, interpretation, semantics, onomastics, denotative, connotative, significative, polysemy, context.

INTRODUCTION.

The development of science and the unprecedented acceleration of socio-political events and economic processes in society affect almost all areas. Faced with the process of globalization, human society is increasingly aware of innovation, discovery and innovation in various fields, as well as the process of their effective use. All things and phenomena that have occurred and been discovered in the history of mankind have their own meaning and understanding, and it is natural that these

meanings and concepts are expressed in words. Everything in the world, events, states, movements, relationships, intellectual discoveries, artificial and natural intelligence, social being as a material and spiritual good, a product of social consciousness, etc. have their own meaning and concept at that time. They have their own name represented by the word. The Bible teaches that the beginning and end of everything is words. Therefore, in the development of New Uzbekistan, on the basis of the development of science, to strengthen the integration of national and universal values, the implementation of the idea of national revival to national progress and the development of a national language policy. additional linguistic research is important.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

In the history of Uzbek linguistics, as well as in world linguistics, scientific studies of the word and its features have a long history. However, the study of the word as a lexical unit in the Uzbek language system and the scientific study of lexicology as a separate branch dates back to the middle of the 20th century. In Uzbek linguistics, the word, that is, the development of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language, its historical development and layers, Professor A. Nurmonov emphasizes that the first information about the place and scientific research belong to the linguist Fakhri Kamol [1,232]. Also, a special approach to the study of the historical layers of Uzbek words and each layer was developed by linguist E. Begmatov [2,5], who studied the meaning of words in Uzbek and, in particular, It is necessary to recognize the researches of linguists G. Kabuljanova [3,4], R.A. Suyunova [4,8] for a deeper study of the aspects of figurative meaning, a detailed interpretation of their linguistic essence. In linguistics, the word and its scientific study occupy a special place.

Linguistically, the word is considered the most important, basic and central unit of language and speech. The linguistic study of many features and phenomena of language and speech begins with the scientific study of the word. The word, which is a unit of speech, is directly related to the activity of speech; it arises in the process of speech. Consequently, the word is a unit of speech, a "wealth" of speech. The word exists in all respects as a real unity, concreteness, clarity. In other words, "a lexeme is

a ready-made and diverse set of possibilities as a unit of language, and a word is a material form in which it has found its event, its realization, its definite form, content and function. Each lexeme appears in speech as a certain word" [13, 141]. Thus, the lexeme and the word are connected by the dialectic of generality and specificity, and the word as a particular is the generality of the lexeme - the actual appearance, movement, performance of a specific task. The word expresses two main aspects of language and speech: expression - sound and content - meaning. The semantic aspects of the word in its various forms are studied semantically in linguistics.

The contemplation of the meaning and function of the word, which is the basic unit of language and speech, is a characteristic feature of any philosophical interest in linguistic research. In this regard, the German linguist G. Kronasser in his works on the history of semantics focused on the classification and interpretation of meaning in the works of Plato (427-347 BC) and Aristotle (384-322 BC), representatives of ancient Greek philosophy emphasizes that the first attempts were made [8,18].

Let us recall the description of the language by Ferdinand de Saussure, the founder of the Geneva School of Linguistics, a well-known linguist, as a source that forms and continuously enriches the human mind and mental abilities [12,23]. It is important to emphasize once again that the "signs of thought" underlined in this definition are words and phrases that express meaning as the basic unit of speech. The importance of the word, such as its expressive power, its ability, and its name, have always been the focus of scholarly attention.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

Before commenting on the meaning of the word, it is important to note that there are differences in the interpretation of the word "meaning" in each language and their interpretation, and we can observe that it is used in a larger sense. For example, in the Uzbek language this concept is explained as follows: "Meaning - [content, concept, idea]: 1. The content of the word, the concept expressed in words ... 2. exactly. content. 3. Certain actions and what can be deduced from them; expression ... 4. The essence of something, what it is; essence..." [14,566].

When studying the semantic expression of a word at the linguistic level, a wide and narrow scope of a given language situation, a distinction between the lexical and grammatical meanings of a word, the level of proper and figurative meanings, and the semantic field of a word are revealed. word, the denotative and connotative functions of its meaning are explained in detail.

The main function of the word in speech activity is the naming, that is, the nominative function, which is associated with various specific objects-objects, events, actions-situations, signs-signs in objective being, expresses them, means, gives a certain meaning, understanding about them. The nominative function of words is studied in the theory of nomenclature, nomenclature or onomasiology [5,68]. In linguistic literature, onomasiology is scientifically interpreted as "a section that teaches the principles and laws of naming and interpreting lexical units of lexicology" [9,81].

Ideas about the meaning of a word and its relation to things and concepts are widespread in linguistics. In this sense, the function of a word differs because of its relation to an object, concept, or another word. As a result, denotative, significatory and structural functions of meaning are formed. For example, the main functions of a word are: value1 - thing1 (or value2 - thing2) - denotative function; value1 - concept1 (or value2 - concept2) - signified function; sense1 - sense2 (or sense2 - sense1) - is interpreted as a structural function [6,72]. In fact, words have different structures depending on their meaning. Therefore, it is necessary to conditionally approach the connection of words with things and concepts. Because not all words mean the name of an object, event or symbol, that is, not all words have a nominative function. In words, nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs perform the function of naming according to their meaning. However, auxiliary words do not perform a nominative function in their expression. In this regard, the linguist N.Ulukov explains the differences between independent and auxiliary words in terms of lexical meaning, nominative function and morphological status:

1. Features of independent words: lexical meaning; performs a nominative function; changes morphologically; can be an independent part of speech.

2. Features of auxiliary words: lack of lexical meaning; used in many auxiliary values and functions; morphologically does not change; cannot act as an independent part of speech [10, 140].

In view of the foregoing, it is also debatable to consider all words in speech conditional. Linguist S. Muminov says that "...not all symbols (names) in the language are conditional. Existing words are used in one sense or another to describe each new concept. But the word chosen to express the new concept is not accidental. It arises from the legal connection between a new concept and an existing word ... In general, each word has a certain lexical meaning, and this meaning serves to express the essence of the expressive to one degree or another" [11, 44].

As mentioned above, words are names that exist in our speech due to their nominative function, which is inherently higher in nature. Words can be basic or correct and figurative. The main or correct meaning of a word is directly related to the nominative function of the term. Transferred words appear based on the base or literal word. As a result, a word expressing the same meaning or concept, thing or event is used to express another thing or event. The use of this word in a figurative sense is characteristic of all languages. As a rule, linguistic translations include metaphors, metonymy, synecdoche and functional transitions.

Words can have different meanings depending on their similarity, proximity and use in speech, and can also add additional meanings to the word. This creates a level of linguistic ambiguity. Each plural meaning of a word is related to the meaning of another word. Linguistically, the expansion of the lexical meaning of a word leads to the formation of polysemantic words. The polysemy of words in linguistics is often called polysemy.

When we think broadly about the meanings of words, we must keep in mind that the lexical meanings of a language are constantly interrelated. It is in this respect that words can have different forms, meanings, and meanings depending on the meaning. This linguistic process generates such linguistic phenomena as homonyms, synonyms, antonyms and paronyms [7,93].

The process by which words are spoken or used in a text is called context. The expressive and semantic aspects of the word, its specific meanings become clearer and more detailed in the process of speech or in the context [5,74]. Context is also interpreted in linguistics as an oral text. A spoken text is a speech work that is complete in content, allowing you to determine the meaning of the words contained in it. The words in such a passage serve as a barrier to each other [15,72], at the same time they serve to fully reveal the expressive meaning of the word, taking into account the context, time, context and place. Linguist, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan Azim Khodjiev in his scientific research, commenting on the above situation, also uses the meaning of the word, which is formed and arises in connection with the spoken text, in the form of a text meaning [15,61].

Clarity of meaning is the application of the rules of speech in speech. Each word has its own scope, use and application. Although they are synonyms, each has its own place. The volume, place and place of the use of a particular word in its meaning are specified by the context, as mentioned above.

The word is the key to speech. Therefore, it is important to know the nature, characteristics and level of meaning of the word. Words differ in their meaning, form, contradiction, pronunciation, doublet and variant, as well as in their ambiguity, correct and figurative usage. A careful study of the meanings of words is necessary not only for the purpose of conveying an idea or accepting an idea, but also for the specific impact of the meaning of a word on the way to the goal of reaching the masses, the majority, society, serving both expressive and emotional.

From the above analysis and examples, it can be seen that the definition or definition of the meaning of a word is not limited by the lexical meanings given in a particular section of the dictionary, but by the content, context, co-volume of these units, as well as the breadth of their semantic field, indicate that that the scope of lamas, imagery, jargon, professionalism, and the presence of its own content as a concept.

CONCLUSION.

According to linguists around the world, there are more than 7,000 languages in the world. Of the 7.5 billion people spoken in the world, only 1%, or 90% of the world's

population, speak 70 languages. The Uzbek language is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, and our language is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. In fact, there are now more than 50 million people in the world, and according to some estimates, about 55 million people speak the Uzbek language [16]. Although due to significant changes in the structure of the Uzbek language dictionary, it becomes necessary to create an explanatory dictionary that meets the requirements of the time, although the 5-volume "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" was compiled and published by a group of lexicographers in 2006-2008, it contained only 80,000 words . The dictionary contains about 80,000 words and phrases widely used in the Uzbek literary language, terms related to science, art, culture and technology, dialects and historical words available [17]. However, the final conclusion about the number of words in the above-mentioned Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language cannot be made. Because, according to the famous linguist, Professor A. Rustamov, the number of words in the Uzbek language is at least 500,000 (five hundred thousand) [18].

A careful study of the semantics of words in our language and a scientific study of the level of meaning of a word as a unit of language, a lexeme as a unit of speech reveals logical clarity and perfection. Compliance with the norms of word usage in accordance with the meaning, understanding and nominative function of speech, ensuring accuracy in all respects guarantees progress in achieving the goals set for society. As the famous 17th-century French philosopher René Descartes said, "If you can understand the meaning of words, you can save the world from semi-disorder."

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